

Linnæus University

Monthly Report May 2026 SENTINEL Wild Birds

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SUMMARY REPORT

1. OVERVIEW

SENTINEL Wild Birds aims to enhance the understanding of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) virus dynamics in wild bird populations by conducting active surveillance at key locations in and near Europe. These locations are divided into the following surveillance nodes: Node 1 Gulf of Finland (Finland, Estonia), Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea (Sweden, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland), Node 3 Western Black Sea (Ukraine), Node 4 Eastern Black Sea (Georgia), Node 5 Wadden Sea (the Netherlands), Node 6 Lake Constance (Germany, Austria, Switzerland), Node 7 Veneto Region (Italy), Node 8 Camargue (France), and Node 9 Gulf of Cadiz (Spain). This monthly summary provides an update on sampled wild birds as part of an early warning system to support wildlife management and disease prevention efforts. The data in this report are based on previously unpublished samples from five nodes, collected from March to May 2026, with a few additional samples from Germany dating back to December 2025.

Note that the numbers presented in this and previous monthly reports are based on data extracts prepared at the time of analysis. As some samples may be re-analysed or reported in more than one period, the numbers reported across different monthly summaries are not strictly additive and may differ slightly from aggregated totals in the underlying dataset.

2. RESULTS

2.1 DATA COLLECTION

Since the last monthly report was published on 30th of April 2026 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19915939>), and as of 15th May 2026, test results have been submitted for 431 samples taken from 410 individuals representing 16 taxa from five nodes in and near Europe (Table 1). Of the 431 collected samples, 196 (45%) were faecal samples, 79 (18%) ticks from nests, 66 (15%) combined swabs (choana + cloacal), 35 (8%) feather swabs, 19 (4%) cloacal swabs, 19 (4%) tracheal/oropharyngeal swabs, and 17 (4%) water samples.

Prevalence and host species sampled

The most sampled species were Yellow-legged Gull (226 individuals), ticks (79 samples), and Lesser Black-backed Gull (50 individuals; Table 1). Only two positive samples were found, one from a Black-headed Gull sampled in Georgia in late March, and one from a Lesser Black-backed Gull sampled in the Netherlands in mid-April (Table 1).

TABLE 1 Most recently sampled individuals in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Total number of individuals sampled in the wild, number of individuals tested positive for avian influenza virus as well as bird-level prevalence. The table includes previously unpublished samples from December 2025 to May 2026.

Group/species	Node 4 Georgia		Node 5 Netherlands		Node 6 Germany		Node 8 France		Node 9 Spain		Total		
	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Prev.
<i>Waterfowl</i>													
Mallard	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0%
Domestic Mallard	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0%
<i>Hérons</i>													
Great Egret	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	7	0	0%
Purple Heron	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	6	0	0%
<i>Waders</i>													
Eurasian Oystercatcher	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0%
Northern Lapwing	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0%
Ruff	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0%
Common Redshank	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0%
Spotted Redshank	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0%
Eurasian Whimbrel	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0%
Jack Snipe	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
<i>Larids</i>													
Black-headed Gull	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	50%
Yellow-legged Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	226	0	0	0	226	0	0%
Lesser Black-backed Gull	0	0	50	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	50	1	2%
<i>Other</i>													
Ticks	0	0	0	0	0	0	79	0	0	0	79	0	0%
Unknown species	0	0	0	0	17	0	0	0	0	0	17	0	0%
Total	8	1	67	1	17	0	305	0	13	0	410	2	0%

HPAI detection

Of all samples, 2 (<1%) tested positive for avian influenza virus, of which none were confirmed as highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) virus (Figure 1; Table 2).

Other AIV detections

None of the two samples testing positive for avian influenza virus (AIV), have yet been subtyped.

FIGURE 1 Sample sites in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Sample sites for the 410 individuals sampled in Georgia, the Netherlands, Germany, France, and Spain. The figure includes previously unpublished samples from December 2025 to May 2026.

A weekly compilation of all 33,992 samples (positive and negative; including previously published), collected at each node from August 2024 to May 2026, can be seen in Figure 2. The proportion of positive individuals (bird-level prevalence) per week over the total project period, for all nodes combined, can be seen in Figure 3.

TABLE 2 Most recently collected samples in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Total number of collected samples as well as number of samples positive for avian influenza virus. The table includes previously unpublished samples from December 2025 to May 2026.

Group/species	Node 4 Georgia			Node 5 Netherlands			Node 6 Germany			Node 8 France			Node 9 Spain			Total		
	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI
<i>Waterfowl</i>																		
Mallard	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0
Domestic Mallard	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0
<i>Hérons</i>																		
Great Egret	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	0	0	14	0	0
Purple Heron	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	12	0	0
<i>Waders</i>																		
Eurasian Oystercatcher	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0
Northern Lapwing	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Ruff	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Common Redshank	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Spotted Redshank	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Eurasian Whimbrel	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Jack Snipe	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
<i>Larids</i>																		
Black-headed Gull	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	1	0
Yellow-legged Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	226	0	0	0	0	0	226	0	0
Lesser Black-backed Gull	0	0	0	50	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	50	1	0
<i>Other</i>																		
Ticks	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	79	0	0	0	0	0	79	0	0
Unknown species	0	0	0	0	0	0	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17	0	0
Total	16	1	0	67	1	0	17	0	0	305	0	0	26	0	0	431	2	0

FIGURE 2 Weekly summary of collected samples in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. In total, 33,992 samples (negative samples in blue; samples positive for avian influenza virus in orange) have been collected at nine nodes between August 2024 and May 2026, yielding 2,306 samples positive for avian influenza virus, including 103 samples positive for HPAI virus. The figures also include samples published in previous reports.

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FIGURE 3 Weekly bird-level prevalence of avian influenza virus in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Weekly prevalence of individuals positive for avian influenza virus from all nodes combined between August 2024 and May 2026, separated for each year. The figures only include bird samples (excluding mussels, ticks, and water samples). The number of individuals (here: any individual bird sampled on a given day) are included at the top of the figure.

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2.2 GENOMICS SUMMARY

Since the last report was published on 30th of April 2026 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19915938>), and as of the 15th of May 2026, five new H5 sequences have been generated from samples positive for avian influenza virus. These samples were collected in Ukraine (Node 3 Eastern Black Sea) and were collected from Mallards. Four of the samples were H5N1, and one was H5Nx.

Genetic analysis of the haemagglutinin (HA) gene sequences from these sequences found that all belonged to the H5 clade 2.3.4.4b of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) (Figure 4A).

Two of the H5 HPAI sequences were classified as the DI.2.1 sub-genotype of the EA-2024-DI genotype, according to the European Union Reference Laboratory for Avian Influenza classification system (<https://github.com/izsvenezie-virology/genin2>), whilst the other three sequences were unclassified due to missing segments. The HA sequences of all five sequences were found to be similar to other DI.2.1 sequences from the SENTINEL Wild Birds project (Figure 4B), as well as elsewhere in Europe.

The Nextstrain builds are available on the SENTINEL Wild Birds Group (<https://nextstrain.org/groups/SentinelWildBirds>).

In addition to the H5 sequences, there have been six non-H5 avian influenza sequences generated from samples collected in Ukraine (Node 3 Western Black Sea). The sequences generated were of the H1N8 (N=1) and H10N7 (N=5) subtypes, with the H1N8 collected from a Eurasian Teal and the H10N7 sequences from Mallards.

This analysis is based on data obtained from the GISAID EpiFlu platform (Elbe and Buckland-Merrett 2017; Shu and McCauley 2017) 15th of May 2026 and is accessible at <https://doi.org/10.55876/gis8.260529fk>. Where sequences were included that are under a publishing embargo at the time of writing, specific permission to utilise these data was obtained from the Data Provider.

A

B

FIGURE 4 Phylogenetic analyses of the H5 HA sequences generated by Node 3 Western Black Sea. A. Image of the H5 HA sequences generated by the SENTINEL Wild Birds project, with the 2.3.4.4b and EA-nonGsGd clades highlighted. **B.** Zoom image of the HA tree focusing on the H5 highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) clade 2.3.4.4b sequences from Node 3 Western Black Sea in relation to other sequences from Europe and surrounding countries. The new sequences generated in this period are highlighted with arrows. In **A** and **B**, tip shapes are coloured according to the sampling node.

3. CONCLUSION

The current reporting period was characterised by a low level of avian influenza virus detection, with only two positive samples identified among more than 400 sampled individuals and no detections of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) virus. The results are consistent with the generally low prevalence observed across several surveillance nodes during late spring.

During this period, five H5 sequences have been generated, all of which from the 2.3.4.4b HPAI clade and two were confirmed to be the DI.2.1 sub-genotype, which has predominated in Europe since mid-September 2025 (EFSA 2025). This sequence demonstrated high similarity to sequences collected across Europe, including other sequences generated by the SENTINEL Wild Birds project which were collected in late 2025. In addition to prior reports, this similarity highlights the connectivity between the active and passive sampling schemes that are ongoing within Europe.

A notable development during this period was the inclusion of tick samples collected from nests in a Yellow-legged Gull colony in Camargue, France. The samples were collected as a part of a project on vector-borne diseases. Although all tick samples tested negative for avian influenza virus, their inclusion broadens the surveillance framework and may provide complementary information on pathogen occurrence in colony environments. The absence of any positive samples in the Yellow-legged Gull colony in the Camargue is noteworthy, given the number of birds and nest-associated tick samples analysed from this site. Future reporting will treat ticks as a sample type associated with an individual bird rather than an independent sampling unit.

Despite the limited number of positive detections, continued surveillance across a wide geographical network remains important for early detection of changes in avian influenza virus circulation and for maintaining a comprehensive understanding of virus dynamics in wild bird populations.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We gratefully acknowledge all data contributors, i.e., the Authors and their Originating laboratories responsible for obtaining the specimens, and their Submitting laboratories for generating the genetic sequence and metadata and sharing via the GISAID Initiative, on which this research is based.

Node 1: LABRIS, Riigi Laboriuuringute ja Riskihindamise Keskus (Estonia); Ruokavirasto, Finnish Food Authority (Finland); University of Turku (Finland)

Node 2: Swedish National Veterinary Institute (SVA) (Sweden); Linnaeus University (Sweden); Institute of Food Safety, Animal Health and Environment "BIOR" (Latvia); National Food and Veterinary Risk Assessment Institute (Lithuania); State Food and Veterinary Service (Lithuania); National Veterinary Research Institute (Poland)

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Node 5: Wageningen Bioveterinary Research (the Netherlands); Erasmus Medical Center (the Netherlands); Netherlands Institute of Ecology, Dutch Centre for Avian Migration and Demography (the Netherlands)

Node 6: Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES) (Austria); Verein für die Betreuung des Naturschutzgebietes Rheindelta (Naturschutzverein Rheindelta) (Austria); Friedrich-Loeffler-Institute (FLI) (Germany); Max-Planck-Institut für Verhaltensbiologie (MPI) (Germany); National Reference Centre for Poultry and Rabbit Diseases (NRGK) (Switzerland); Swiss Institute for Virology and Immunology (IVI) (Switzerland)

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Node 8: École Nationale Vétérinaire de Toulouse (ENVT); INRAE (Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement); La Tour du Valat; Conservatoire d'Espaces Naturels d'Occitanie (CEN Occitanie); Laboratoire Départemental du Gard; Office Français de la Biodiversité (OFB); Ministère de l'Agriculture et de la Souveraineté Alimentaire; Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle (MNHN); Agence nationale de sécurité sanitaire de l'alimentation, de l'environnement et du travail (ANSES)

Node 9: Martina Ferraguti, Josué Martínez-de la Puente, and Jordi Figuerola at Estación Biológica de Doñana (EBD-CSIC); Ursula Höfle at Grupo de Sanidad y Biotecnología (SaBio), Instituto de Investigación en Recursos Cinegéticos (IREC-CSIC); Elisa Pérez-Ramírez and Jovita Fernández-Pinero at Centro de Investigación en Sanidad Animal (CISA-INIA-CSIC) (Spain).